

The role of economic and geographical factors in the development of countries

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Abstract

The article analyzes that Montesquieu's socio-philosophical views are quite different from others, that in his philosophy, the first level of attention is focused on economic and geographical factors, that the development of countries is related to the geographical environment, and the existence of three bases of this geographical environment: climate, soil and topography.

Key words: climate, soil, topography, environment, economy, development.

Another French thinker, Montesquieu, who was elected to the French Academy in 1728 at the age of 39, had a different socio-philosophical view than others. This difference is that in his philosophy, the first level of attention is focused on economic and geographical factors. Montesque considers the development of the production of material goods through agriculture and crafts as the most important condition for improving people's lives¹. A very wise and forward thinking comment. If you think about it like this, most of the philosophers or scientists engaged in the science of philosophy choose the life of a person and society as a philosophical object, and debates are held on the topics of how to

¹ Salimov Bakhriddin Lutfullaevich. The Importance of Sea Transport in the Communication System. WEB OF SYNERGY: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. 2023. Volume 2 Issue 1, 272-275.

improve the life of a person and how to improve the development of society². And in this process, many thinkers put forward ideas of general content and tried to justify its importance and necessity for the life of man and society. However, there are scholars who show that the correctness of the opinions expressed by them is relevant in all times. There is no need to prove it. It can be said that this opinion has not lost its importance even before Montesquieu, in his time and even now. Only now, various branches and directions of modern production have been added to agriculture and handicrafts. And the material goods they produce today serve to make our lives easier with you. Currently, there are more than 230 countries in the world. The stages of development of these countries and the lifestyle of the population are at different stages. Some are highly developed, others are moderately developed, and the rest are lagging behind. Analyzing the socio-economic conditions of countries that have developed at a high level and created a decent lifestyle for their residents, it is shown that there are a number of factors. One of the most important factors is the establishment of production based on modern technologies in industry and agriculture. In economic terms, this is the growth of gross domestic product and its weight per capita at a high level. Therefore, as in the developed countries of the world, great attention is paid to support and development of production in Uzbekistan.

We noted above that there are a number of reasons why countries are at one or another level of development. In this regard, another unique idea was put forward in Montesquieu's teaching. "He attributes these reasons to the geographical

² Salimov Baxriddin Lutfullaevich. The philosophical role of dialectical categories in human life. *Oriental Renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*. Volume: 1, Issue 6, 2021. P.406-410.

environment. It shows the three bases of the geographical environment: climate, soil and topography.³ Now let's dwell on this idea in detail. Let's look at the world map and then pay attention to the development indicators of the countries. The following cases are noticeable⁴:

- First, it has direct access to the sea and the presence of other communication links;
- Secondly, ownership of oil, gas, gold, uranium and many other useful natural resources;
- Thirdly, the level of development of the surrounding countries and the socio-political and economic situation in that region;
- Fourthly, the climatic conditions of that country (weather, land structure, fertile soil, etc.).

In fact, one or another of the above factors has a decisive importance in the development of countries. For example, one of the sources of development of Arab countries is oil. Also, let's analyze the role of factors in the context of a real life in our recent past. As we know, in December 1991, a great country called the USSR disintegrated. In its place, 15 independent states were formed. To date, these countries have different levels of development indicators and population welfare indices. It must be said frankly, that the Baltic countries of Latvia, Lithuania and Estonia have achieved much higher indicators in this regard. Well why? Answer: the direct access to the sea and the high level of development of the surrounding

³ Salimov Bakhriddin Lutfullaevich. The Importance of Sea Transport in the Communication System. WEB OF SYNERGY: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal. 2023. Volume 2 Issue 1, 272-275.

⁴ Салимов Б.Л. Ижтимоий муносабатларнинг коммуникация ва транспорт тизими билан детерминистик боғлиқлигининг гносеологик таҳлили. Фалсафа фанлари доктори диссертацияси. Ўзбекистон Миллий университети. Тошкент. 2022, 224 б.

countries, as well as the stable socio-political and economic situation in this region⁵. We can say without hesitation that if Uzbekistan had these opportunities, the level of development of Uzbekistan would be much higher than theirs. It should be noted that our geographical location is a bit inconvenient in this regard. Among all the countries in the world, only two countries have to pass through the territory of two countries to reach the sea. One of them is Uzbekistan. However, despite this, Uzbekistan continues to take bold steps along the path of development it has chosen. Currently, our trade relations with the countries of the world are conducted mainly through Kazakhstan and Russia, but in the future, in the southern direction, through Turkmenistan-Iran and Afghanistan-Iran, Afghanistan-Pakistan, and in the eastern direction, through Kyrgyzstan-China, we are struggling with the possibilities of access to the sea (We we will discuss this in detail in the next parts of our scientific work).

Montesquieu makes another unique comment on this topic. Now he reflects on the impact of living in fertile and infertile soil areas on human life. And in Montesquieu's view, living in barren lands “leads men to discovery, to oppression, to hard work, to courage, to war; after all, they are forced to create what they did not give soil. All this leads to the establishment of a republican "governance" method in countries with infertile soil⁶. Now, it is impossible to agree one hundred percent with this conclusion of the scholar. This reasoning can be approached from

⁵ Salimov Baxriddin Lutfullaevich. The philosophical role of dialectical categories in human life. *Oriental Renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*. Volume: 1, Issue 6, 2021. - P.406-410.

⁶ Салимов Б.Л. Ижтимоий муносабатларнинг коммуникация ва транспорт тизими билан детерминистик боғлиқлигининг гносеологик таҳлили. Фалсафа фанлари доктори диссертацияси. Ўзбекистон Миллий университети. Тошкент. 2022, 224 б.

two sides. One is the aspect we agree with, the other is the aspect we deny. True, we agree: in reality, living in areas with barren soil and harsh conditions is tough for people. They work tirelessly to overcome the vagaries of the existing nature, to get the expected harvest from that barren soil. Otherwise, life forces them to find other ways to make ends meet. For example, in the conditions of our Uzbekistan, there are areas with unproductive, fertile or saline soils. It can be said that due to the timely and perfect implementation of the necessary agrotechnical activities by our hardworking people, our hardworking grandfather farmers, entrepreneurial farmers, the task of growing the expected harvest from these fields is being accomplished with great effort.

We do not agree with the wrong aspects: the above considerations should not lead to the conclusion that the peoples living in areas with extremely fertile soil will not be hardworking, inquisitive, and capable. After all, there are many fertile soil areas in the world. And there are places in these areas where the level of socio-economic development is much higher. Then, we need to note one thing that the level of socio-economic development is not high in all regions with infertile soil. This is also true. So, the conclusion is that whether people are hardworking, gifted, capable or not is highly dependent on whether they live in areas with fertile soil or infertile soil. Also, different types of people can live in areas with fertile soil and areas with infertile soil. Among them there are hard workers and there are lazy people⁷.

We cannot agree with Montesquieu's contention that republican governance

⁷ Salimov Baxriddin Lutfullaevich. The philosophical role of dialectical categories in human life. *Oriental Renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*. Volume: 1, Issue 6, 2021. P.406-410.

is established only in countries with infertile soil. After all, both in Montesque's time and later, historical facts proved that the republican way of governance was established not only in countries with infertile soil, but also in countries with fertile soil. However, Montesquieu has a number of other socio-political views that were far ahead of his time. For example, Montesquieu has the following opinion: "Political freedom is impossible without the division of legislative, executive and judicial powers, not only in the monarchy, but also in the republic. Each of them is independent from each other in performing their tasks and they perform them through certain institutions. Immanuel Kant, a famous German philosopher who lived after Montesquieu, expressed a similar conclusion to this reasoning⁸. The correctness of this idea, as soon as you glance at it, will settle in your mind like lightning. Because let's not take as an example any country known to us in the world political scene in modern times, they all have the three types of power that Montesquieu mentioned, that is, the legislative, executive and judicial powers. And they function independently of each other and each as a separate institution, as Montesquieu mentioned. Therefore, these three types of power have their own status, they work only according to the established laws and cannot interfere or interfere with each other's activities. In particular, such a procedure is in force in our Uzbekistan. It should be mentioned that in recent years there have been many positive changes and updates in our country regarding the organization and improvement of the activities of the above three authorities.

⁸ Салимов Б.Л. Ижтимоий муносабатларнинг коммуникация ва транспорт тизими билан детерминистик боғлиқлигининг гносеологик таҳлили. Фалсафа фанлари доктори диссертацияси. Ўзбекистон Миллий университети. Тошкент. 2022, 224 б.

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